

Synthesis and Characterisation of Antimony(III)bis(diisopropylthio-phosphate)alkylxanthates

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Dialkyldithiophosphate and alkylxanthate ligands are versatile in nature and can exhibit different types of bonding patterns with metals^{1,2}. A number of antimony(III)²⁻⁵ tris as well as organoantimony(III)⁶ derivatives of these ligands have been reported. However, comparatively less attention has been paid to the mixed sulphur ligand complexes of antimony. We have recently reported some mixed dithiolato-antimony(III) derivatives of these ligands^{7,8}. Antimony derivatives with dithiophosphorous ligands have also been reported to exhibit antitumor activity⁹.

In the present communication, we report some mixed ligand complexes of antimony(III) of the type [(i-C₃H₇O)₂PS₂]₂SbS₂COR (where, R = Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ and Buⁱ).

Results and Discussion

Antimony(III)bis(diisopropylthiophosphate)alkylxanthates have been synthesised by the reaction of monochloroantimony(III)bis(diisopropylthiophosphate) with potassium alkylxanthates in equimolar ratios in benzene.

where, R = Et, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ and Buⁱ.

These derivatives (Table 1) are yellow viscous liquids and are soluble in common organic solvents, like benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and alcohols. On heating, these tend to decompose, therefore the reactions were carried out at room temperature. These derivatives decompose

slowly on standing for a few days even at room temperature.

The infrared spectra of these derivatives have been recorded. Tentative assignments have been made on the basis of earlier reports^{4,5}.

The coordinate analysis in Ni^{II}-xanthates¹⁰ show that the bands are highly coupled in the ir spectra of such complexes. The complexes revealed ir bands at 1 225–1 240 (C–O–C), 1 120–1 160 (C...O) and 1 020–1 030 cm⁻¹ (C...S). The appearance of the only one band at 1 025 cm⁻¹ (C...S) indicates the bidentate¹¹ nature of the alkylxanthate ligand in these complexes. The bands at 970–985 and 810–820 cm⁻¹ are assigned to (P)–O–C and P–O–(C) stretching modes respectively. A strong band due to P=S present in the spectra of sodium salts of dialkyldithiophosphoric acid at 660–690 cm⁻¹ shifted towards lower frequencies in the spectra of these derivatives at 640–650 cm⁻¹. This shifting indicates most probably a strong bidentate chelation of dithiophosphate ligand with antimony⁸. Bands of medium intensity at 530–560 and 320–330 cm⁻¹ due to (P–S) and (Sb–S) stretching vibrations respectively.

Pmr spectra of these derivatives reveal a doublet at δ 1.40 for methyl protons and a heptate at δ 4.92 for CHO protons of diisopropylthiophosphate group. In addition these compounds exhibit characteristic proton resonances of the corresponding alkylxanthate moieties as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF MONOCHLOROANTIMONY(III)BIS(DIISOPROPYLDITHIOPHOSPHATE) WITH POTASSIUM ALKYLXANTHATES*

Sl. no.	[(i-C ₃ H ₇ O) ₂ PS ₂] ₂ SbCl (g)	KS ₂ COR R (g)	Product [(i-C ₃ H ₇ O) ₂ PS ₂] ₂ SbS ₂ COR R (% yield)	Empirical formula	Sb% Found/Calcd.
1.	1.78	Et (0.49)	C ₃ H ₅ (96)	C ₁₅ H ₃₃ S ₆ O ₅ Sb	18.81 (18.23)
2.	1.55	Pr ⁿ (0.46)	C ₃ H ₇ ⁿ (99)	C ₁₆ H ₃₅ S ₆ O ₅ Sb	18.98 (17.86)
3.	1.68	Pr ⁱ (0.50)	C ₃ H ₇ ⁱ (82)	C ₁₆ H ₃₅ S ₆ O ₅ Sb	18.83 (17.86)
4.	1.73	Bu ⁿ (0.56)	C ₄ H ₉ ⁿ (96)	C ₁₇ H ₃₇ S ₆ O ₅ Sb	18.06 (17.5)
5.	1.36	Bu ⁱ (0.44)	C ₄ H ₉ ⁱ (97)	C ₁₇ H ₃₇ S ₆ O ₅ Sb	18.85 (17.5)

*Molar ratio, 1 : 1; all compounds gave satisfactory C, H and S analysis.

TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA FOR ALKYLXANTHATE ANTIMONY(III)-BIS(DIISOPROPYLDITHIOPHOSPHATE)

Compd.	δ
$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2Sb.S_2COC_2H_5$	1.47 (27H, m, CH ₃), 4.73 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.3 Hz, OCH ₂), 4.92 (4H, h, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH)
$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2Sb.S_2COC_3H_7^a$	1.02 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, CH ₃), 1.40 (24H, d, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂), 1.92 (2H, m, CH ₂), 4.60 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂), 4.92 (4H, h, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH)
$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2Sb.S_2COC_3H_7^b$	1.40 (30H, d, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₃), 4.92 (4H, h, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH), 5.69 (1H, h, <i>J</i> 6.2 Hz, OCH xanthate)
$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2Sb.S_2COC_4H_9^a$	1.02 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, CH ₃), 1.4 (24H, d, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂), 1.85 (4H, m, CH ₂), 4.60 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂), 4.92 (4H, h, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH)
$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2Sb.S_2COC_4H_9^b$	1.02 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, CH ₃ xanthate), 1.40 (24H, d, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH ₂), 1.92 (1H, m, CH), 4.60 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 6.0 Hz, OCH ₂), 4.92 (4H, h, <i>J</i> 6.5 Hz, CH)

The earlier reports as well as the above mentioned studies indicate bidentate mode of attachment of both types of ligands to antimony which leads to a distorted octahedral geometry particularly when the presence of stereochemically active lone-pair of electron is also considered in the coordination sphere.

Experimental

All experiments were carried out under moisture-free conditions. Solvents (benzene, carbondisulphide, ethanol, n-propanol, i-propanol, n-butanol, i-butanol) were dried by standard methods. Monochloroantimony(III)bis(diisopropylidithiophosphate)⁴ and potassium alkylxanthates¹² were prepared by reported methods. Antimony was estimated iodometrically and sulphur gravimetrically as barium sulphate. C and H were analysed at Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre of Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Pye-Unican SP3 300 spectrometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Zeol FX-90 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard.

$[(i-C_3H_7O)_2PS_2]_2SbS_2COC_2H_5$: A mixture of potassium ethylxanthate (0.49 g; 3.06 mmol) and monochloroantimony(III)bis(diisopropylidithiophosphate) (1.78 g; 3.06 mmol) in benzene (25 ml) was stirred for ~4 h at room temperature. The precipitated KCl was removed by filtration. On removal of solvent from the filtrate, viscous yellow product was obtained (1.97 g; 98%). Other derivatives were prepared in the similar manner.

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